

A Model Based Implementation of an IoT Framework

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Abstract—The growing complexity of the Industrial Internet of Things (IoT) necessitates robust methodologies for efficient system development and deployment. This paper introduces a model-based code structure that implements an IoT framework, streamlining system development for engineers, simplifying deployment for technicians, and ensuring compliance with industry standards. Key design principles explored in this work include resilience, interoperability, cybersecurity, and semantic reasoning—critical for building scalable IoT solutions. To validate this approach, we present a climate control use case alongside industrial system implementations that integrate OPC UA, Modbus, and MQTT.

Index Terms—Service-oriented systems engineering, Cyber-physical systems, Systems engineering education

I. INTRODUCTION

Once upon a time, there were telephone directories. These were known as the White Pages and Yellow Pages. They were thick softcover books, published annually. The White Pages listed the telephone subscribers from a specific area in alphabetical order with their address and telephone number. The Yellow Pages listed businesses in alphabetical order by the type of the services they offered. So, if anybody had a clogged kitchen sink, their fingers would just have to walk across the Yellow Pages to find a suitable plumber. Once contacted, the plumber would, with a smile, come to clear the clogged drain. It should be noted that the Yellow Pages only exposed the registered services, such as those offered by a plumber or a plumbing company. The plumber himself is not a service but a resource, with an address and a phone number. It is the plumber's skills that are exposed as services.

The Internet has revolutionized our society and rendered the White and Yellow Pages obsolete. Today, people swipe across their Internet-connected devices to find the services they need, having long forgotten the directories.

As computing devices have shrunk in size and cost while increasing in power, their impact has extended from societal applications into industrial domains. The Internet revolution accelerated in the late 20th century, gaining momentum with the rise of the World Wide Web. Industries soon integrated the Internet to facilitate communication between devices and systems. This expansion has fueled movements like Germany's Industry 4.0 and the Industry IoT Consortium (IIC) in the United States [1], [2]. These movements are part of the so-called fourth industrial revolution, which standardizes and

expands the way “things” communicate, forming the Internet of Things (IoT).

The rise of IoT has disrupted industrial structures, transforming the traditional ISA-95 hierarchical model into a decentralized network of interconnected systems. To ensure structure and manage the complexity, researchers and industry leaders have proposed various reference architectures and frameworks. Examples include the reference architecture for Industry 4.0 (RAMI 4.0) and the Industrial Internet Reference Architecture (IIRA). These architectures serve as blueprints for designing interoperable and scalable systems [3]–[5]. Proprietary solutions, such as AWS IoT and Microsoft Azure IoT, are widely adopted in industrial applications [6]. European frameworks, such as FIWARE and the Arrowhead framework, provide additional solutions, particularly within European-funded initiatives [6].

These frameworks provide valuable guidance, but implementing them poses significant challenges. Developers must translate abstract concepts into functional, real-world systems, a process that is both conceptually and technically demanding. This work explores how Model-Based Systems Engineering (MBSE) can facilitate the transformation from abstract models to operational systems.

MBSE employs models as the fundamental mechanism for capturing, analyzing, communicating, and validating system requirements, design, and behavior throughout the system lifecycle, shifting away from traditional document-centric approaches [7], [8]. This work supports the claim that MBSE can ease system development by providing clear, structured models that simplify the transformation from framework to code [9]. Compared to traditional coding approaches, MBSE allows rapid prototyping and validation before deployment, reducing integration effort [10]. Furthermore, and central to this work, MBSE enhances knowledge transfer to technicians and engineers, fostering system resilience through improved understanding. The overarching vision of this work is to enable the training of a deployment technician within half a day and a development engineer within one day. This vision will be substantiated if the proposed concept is accepted and gains traction within the relevant community.

For effective IoT deployment, several studies have emphasized the critical role of workforce education. These studies underscore the necessity of skill development for the

successful implementation of IoT solutions. Valmohammadi highlights the need for investments in IT infrastructure and employee education to accelerate IoT adoption in organizations [11]. Given the steep learning curve of IoT technologies, structured learning programs are essential for equipping engineers with the necessary expertise. After reading this article, readers should be able to assess their familiarity with various IoT implementations and understand the factors influencing their preferences.

This paper demonstrates the application of MBSE to the Arrowhead framework, leveraging the Go programming language (also known as Golang) for its implementation. The source code is publicly available as an open-source project on GitHub¹. In the following sections, the Arrowhead framework is briefly introduced, followed by a multifaceted model of the framework that is subsequently packaged into a library. To demonstrate the capabilities of the library, a climate control use case—modeled as a local cloud or system of systems—is presented. Other systems that integrate technologies that rely on Modbus, OPC UA, and MQTT to support broader industrial solutions are presented. Finally, a discussion addresses key topics including resilience, interoperability (encompassing both protocol and semantic interoperability), backwards compatibility, cybersecurity, and semantic reasoning.

II. THE ARROWHEAD FRAMEWORK

The Arrowhead framework was developed to improve automation and secure interoperability in the European manufacturing industry. It originated from European Union-funded projects aimed at modernizing communication between legacy, current, and future industrial systems. The framework adheres to a low-latency, service-oriented architecture, enabling direct and secure system-to-system communication [12]. To ensure confidentiality and trust, it employs public key infrastructure for encryption and authentication.

In the context of IoT, each entity consists of a “thing” and an interfacing software that connects the thing to the cyber world and the Internet. The “thing” can be a physical device like a sensor or actuator, or it can be a more abstract asset such as an algorithm or database. In RAMI 4.0 terms, the thing is called an asset, and the software that interacts with it is called a shell. A paradigm of the Arrowhead framework combines the software and asset into what it calls a system. In this work, we use the terms “husk” for the software interface and “unit asset” for the underlying resource. This distinction helps highlight the differences between RAMI 4.0 and the Arrowhead framework concerning asset administration shells.

The Arrowhead framework’s service-oriented architecture emulates the Yellow Pages analogy introduced earlier. Just as the Yellow Pages registered available services from different businesses, the Arrowhead framework’s Service Registrar maintains a directory of currently available services provided by various systems. Each system registers the functionalities of its unit assets as services, making them discoverable and

Fig. 1. A block definition diagram representation of an Arrowhead system.

consumable by other systems at run time, which is referred as late binding.

The framework provides three core systems to manage the service lifecycle: the Service Registrar, the Orchestrator, and the authorization system. When a system seeks a service, it contacts the Orchestrator, which queries the Service Registrar for available services and consults the authorization system to validate access permissions. The Orchestrator returns the service’s resource location, enabling direct consumption by the system making the inquiry.

One of the key features of the Arrowhead framework is its fine-grained service authorization mechanism. For example, a data logger may be authorized to access the state of an actuator but not to modify it, while a controller system may have permission to both read and write actuator states.

A distinctive aspect of the Arrowhead framework is the concept of a local cloud, which consists of a set of systems that operate autonomously while retaining the capability to communicate with other clouds when needed [13]. Each local cloud must have a Service Registrar, Orchestrator, and an authorization system to maintain autonomy and security. Although the size of a local cloud is not predefined, it must remain within practical limits to ensure efficient operation. For secure cross-cloud interactions, the framework puts forward the GateKeeper and Gateway systems [14].

With the overall concepts of the Arrowhead framework presented, the next step is to model this understanding. In the following section, we demonstrate how the framework can be modeled using both structural and behavioral diagrams, facilitating a clearer understanding of its components and their interactions.

III. MODELING THE FRAMEWORK

Visual modeling languages offer a standardized method for depicting the design and structure of systems. Common examples include the Unified Modeling Language (UML) and the Systems Modeling Language (SysML) [15], [16]. These languages define a taxonomy of diagrams categorized into two main types: structural and behavioral diagrams. Both are necessary to comprehensively represent system architecture and interactions.

To begin, the structural aspects of the Arrowhead framework must be defined. A local cloud consists of systems running on

¹<https://github.com/sdoque>

Fig. 2. Use cases for a generic Arrowhead system, showing interactions within a local cloud.

devices, each system consisting of a husk and one or more unit assets. The husk is responsible for exposing the functionalities of the unit assets as services that other systems can consume. It relies on protocol specific servers to intercept the requests. Figure 1 depicts a class or block definition diagram of a system. This high-level model emphasizes the relationships among systems, unit assets, and services. Each system runs on a single device, has exactly one husk, and contains one or more unit assets. Each unit asset provides at least one service and may also consume services.

Next, the behavioral aspects of the Arrowhead framework are defined to capture the dynamic interactions between systems. Figure 2 illustrates the main use cases for a generic Arrowhead system. The term generic here implies that all Arrowhead systems utilize these use cases. On the left, the deployment technician appears as the sole human actor, playing a crucial role in system configuration. All other actors represent systems operating within the same local cloud. One key implementation stipulation is that all systems must register their services with the leading Service Registrar, including itself. Service discovery is managed by the Orchestrator. The authorization use case is missing because it has not yet been completed in the current implementation.

On the right side of Figure 2, the interaction between the system and its unit assets is illustrated. This interaction is well-defined for physical unit assets, where the system directly interfaces with external devices such as sensors, actuators, and external software assets such as a database. If the unit asset is an algorithm (e.g. a close loop controller), it may be integrated within the system, encapsulating intellectual property.

Modeling both the structural and behavioral aspects of the framework enhances communication among stakeholders. These models ensure a common understanding of the systems' architecture and streamline software implementation by providing a visual reference for system components and interactions.

IV. THE IMPLEMENTATION

Implementing a reference architecture or framework, even when well-modeled, presents significant challenges. During

Fig. 3. Package organization of the mbaigo repository on GitHub.

implementation, subtle details emerge, often introducing unforeseen complexities.

One of the core strengths of MBSE is its independence from specific reference architectures, frameworks, or programming languages. In other words, MBSE can and should be applied to any software solution due to its effectiveness.

The implementation is made available through two GitHub repositories: one for the library, called mbaigo², and another for a collection of systems. The mbaigo library is composed of three packages: components, forms, and use cases.

The components package contains the core entities such as system, device, husk, unit asset, and service, which are introduced in the previous section (see Figure 1). The use-cases package corresponds to the primary use cases of the Arrowhead framework, such as service registration, discovery, and consumption as illustrated in Figure 2. Finally, the forms package addresses the information exchange payloads and their schemas. Figure 3 illustrates this package organization.

The systems repository contains several example systems that demonstrate how to use the mbaigo library. Each system is organized into two files: 'systemname.go' (e.g., orchestrator.go) and 'thing.go'. This separation is intended for pedagogical reasons, where systemname.go deals with the husk and thing.go acts toward the unit asset. The thing.go file models the unit asset with its configurable attributes, and is the interaction use case, the yellow ellipse of Figure 2.

Figure 4 presents the activity diagram of the 'main()' function located in the systems.go file, illustrating its execution flow. The main() function of each system instantiates and aggregates components from the mbaigo library when starting the system. The system is then configured with support of a file stored alongside the executable. If the configuration file is missing, the system automatically generates one and then shuts down, prompting the deployment technician to update it.

The system generates a private key and requests an X.509 certificate from the Certificate Authority system, if the latter is deployed in the local cloud and operational. The keys are not stored on the file system and exist only in memory during execution. When the program terminates, the memory is released, and both the keys and certificates are lost. When certificates are used for secure communication, mutual authentication is required, meaning both the client and the server must have a valid certificate. At the time of writing, the authentication system has not yet been completed. While

²mbaigo stands for Model-Based Arrowhead Implementation in Go.

Fig. 4. Activity diagram of the ‘main()’ function of all mbaigo systems. The green blocks are concurrent processes (goroutines), which all terminate upon an external request.

secure communication is possible, full cybersecurity cannot be guaranteed, as all certificate requests are currently being issued without authentication. Both software and hardware authentication within mbaigo are under development.

After completing its configuration, the system instantiates and starts the unit assets with the specified settings, and registers their services. This registration process recurs at regular intervals to ensure the leading Service Registrar maintains an up-to-date registry of available services. If the system fails to renew its registration, the Service Registrar removes outdated entries to prevent stale information. Like the operations of unit assets, service renewal processes run concurrently, leveraging lightweight goroutines (green blocks in Figure 4). Finally, the system starts its protocol specific servers to listen for incoming requests.

Upon receiving a shutdown request, the system deregisters all its services, stops its servers, and disconnects from its unit assets. This structured process ensures the system shuts down gracefully.

Each system hosts an HTTP server, which enables it to serve a web page for the deployment technician to verify the installation using a standard web browser. The web pages display real-time information about the system, the device it runs on, its unit assets, and their services. At startup, the system provides the web page address via the command-line interface.

V. THE PROTOTYPES

Prototypes play a critical role in refining implementations and facilitating knowledge transfer. This work introduces several prototype systems, all available in the systems repository, five of which demonstrate the concept of a local cloud. The other systems feature unit assets such as a camera, a microphone, an OPC UA client, a Modbus master, and an

Fig. 5. Representation of a climate control local cloud.

MQTT broker, illustrating seamless asset integration within a local cloud.

The local cloud demonstrator is designed around a climate control use case, showcasing practical applications of service-based interactions. This cloud consists of five systems: a Service Registrar, an Orchestrator, a 1-wire temperature sensor (ds18b20), a pulse-width modulated servo motor emulating a valve (parallax), and a thermostat (see Figure 5). Registered services can be reviewed via the Service Registrar’s query service, just as a deployment technician would when using a web browser. At run time, the thermostat system dynamically discovers the temperature and valve services. Any change in the measured temperature results is a change in the valve position to attain the desired room temperature.

Once the local cloud is operational, one can evaluate the behavior of this system of systems with single system failures to highlights its resilience and adaptability. If the Service Registrar shuts down, systems attempting to re-register their services log a warning; previously discovered services continue to be available since they originate from other systems. If another Service Registrar is part of the local cloud, it assumes the role of the lead registrar. If the Orchestrator shuts down, its shutdown has no immediate impact, as it is only used during service discovery. If the services have not been discovered, the thermostat systems issue a warning every time it seeks its required services. If a service provider ceases operation, the thermostat system logs an error message with a 503 status code and resumes normal operation once the provider comes back online. If the thermostat system stops, no systems are affected unless another system depends on its services.

The thermostat system offers, per unit asset, three services: set point, thermal error, and jitter. The set point service allows users to read or update the thermostat’s target temperature for a room. The thermal error is simply the difference between the measured temperature and set point. The jitter service reports the time taken to complete the two requests (temperature reading and valve position update), which is consistently under ten milliseconds. This setup easily extends to a low cost demand response solution to save energy in smart cities [17].

Other systems can be integrated into the local cloud. The programmable logic controller (PLC) systems on GitHub provide access to the PLC's input and output signals, and memory registers. The UAclient system, featuring an OPC UA client as a unit asset, provides browsing and access services to nodes. By default, the object folder node is available, allowing the deployment technician to navigate through all available nodes and select those of interest to be added to the configuration file. The Modbus system, on the other hand, requires prior knowledge of the PLC's register map, which must be included in the system's configuration file. Another popular IoT protocol, MQTT, operates on a broker-based publish-subscribe model. The Telegrapher system features an MQTT broker as an asset and metamorphoses topics into Arrowhead services.

The camera system, featuring a Raspberry Pi camera as an asset, provides image capture as a service in response to a request. Instead of returning the image directly, the system returns a JSON response specifying the image location and timestamp. A second request is required to retrieve the image file as a JPEG, demonstrating file exchange within a service-based architecture. The Recorder system operates similarly, providing sound recordings. It uses a USB-connected microphone as an asset.

Readers are encouraged to explore the GitHub repositories to gain a deeper understanding of these prototypes. The models in Figures 1 through 4 serve as maps for navigating the repositories. Simpler systems, such as the temperature sensor or camera, offer an entry point before exploring more complex systems like the Service Registrar. The Service Registrar is the most intricate system, incorporating an embedded SQL database and a scheduler that manages the automated cleanup of expired service registrations.

These prototypes illustrate the implementation and deployment of the Arrowhead framework in real-world scenarios. MBSE enables the rapid development of systems with diverse assets. In the next section, we explore key aspects such as resilience, interoperability, cybersecurity, and semantic reasoning within a local cloud environment.

VI. DISCUSSION

The goal of this work is to facilitate knowledge transfer through the use of Model-Based Systems Engineering. The reader should by now have a comprehensive understanding of the current implementation of the IoT framework, as guided by the model diagrams and repository examples. Using MBSE to engineer both the structure and behavior of systems supports this goal while offering additional benefits that are not immediately obvious.

One significant advantage of a service-oriented architecture, such as in the Arrowhead framework, is its loose coupling of systems. This allows systems to be developed independently and integrated dynamically at run time. For example, the temperature sensor system provides its temperature service without knowing how other systems use it. Similarly, the thermostat system is agnostic to whether the temperature

reading comes from a 1-wire system or a PLC with a K-type thermocouple, as long as the service matches its requirements (service definition, unit, and location).

Similarly, the use cases represented in Figure 2 and implemented in the 'usecases' package of the mbaigo library exhibit loose coupling. Each use case is independent and depends only on the components and forms packages. This enables the continuous evolution and refinement of each use case while minimizing impact on overall system functionality. As a result, the framework can evolve continuously without requiring major redesigns.

Interoperability also applies to payload formats. To ensure backward compatibility, exchanged payloads or 'forms' are versioned, ensuring seamless communication between older and newer systems as the data schema evolves. This is done by including a version field within the payload, allowing precise mapping of data to object attributes. Technically, 'forms' in the third package are based on a Go interface, which all forms must implement. The mbaigo library facilitates this process by providing packing and unpacking functions that handle payload serialization in XML and JSON, ensuring correct marshaling into the appropriate schemas.

At startup, each system generates a systemconfig.json file if it is missing, ensuring a uniform configuration process while preserving system-specific data. This approach applies the same configuration use case code across all systems, even future ones, resulting in consistent configuration management. To introduce a new system, a development engineer only needs to model its unit asset, as the same configuration code is reused from the library.

Ensuring efficiency in the development, deployment, and maintenance of IoT systems is essential. MBSE streamlines maintenance by managing updates within use cases in the shared library, ensuring seamless propagation across all systems. This efficiency also strengthens security, particularly when using public key infrastructure. Automating key and certificate generation at system startup simplifies secure system deployment, mitigates security risks, and reduces both cost and complexity.

In an industrial plant, systems and hardware may undergo changes or experience failures. Resilience to such disturbance must be addressed, and redundancy alleviate some of the consequences. The climate control example examined single failure modes; however, extending it to multiple failure modes is straightforward. Since both systems and assets are distributed, analyzing different failure scenarios becomes essential to confirm resiliency.

The husk of a physical asset acts as a digital twin, that is a digital representation of the asset. Consider a power-constrained sensor as an asset, such as a Bluetooth Low Energy temperature sensor running on battery. Its husk, running on a powered computer, provides the sensor service in a way indistinguishable from the previously mentioned 1-wire temperature system. Similarly, a unit asset itself can function as a digital twin. For example, Wintercorn et al. developed a complete CAD model of a factory in Siemens NX with

Modeling and Control Design (MCD), integrating PLCSIM Advanced for automation and using OPC UA to communicate with the Arrowhead framework [18].

Clearly defined data models, such as those in the components package, establish the foundation for developing information models, such as those used in the Semantic Web. The Kgrapher system, available in the systems repository, provides the local cloud's knowledge graph as a service at any point during operations. When combined with the Arrowhead framework ontology, a reasoner can infer new knowledge about the local cloud, detect and report inconsistencies. This technology empowers stakeholders to embrace digital transformation by transitioning from information to knowledge [19]. For instance, one can infer that a local cloud is functional with one Service Registrar but gains resiliency with multiple registrars. Furthermore, this implementation provides semantic interoperability, as it can integrate upper ontologies [20].

A key aspect of digital transformation is using information to guide business decisions, making value chains a critical consideration. Understanding how value is added to products during manufacturing, along with the related costs, is fundamental. Services provided by various assets—such as milling an aluminum block or maintaining an office at 20°C—may incur costs. The unit cost of a service can be set in the configuration file and accessed or modified via the /cost service endpoint. If a service has a defined unit cost, it is also represented in the knowledge graph.

To assist knowledge transfer, three types of documentation are available. First, README.md files are included in the repositories to describe the systems and their purpose. Second, online 'black box' documentation is available through the system's web server, allowing deployment technicians to verify system configurations using a standard web browser. Third, 'white box' documentation is generated using Go Doc, providing detailed insights into its internal architecture. This documentation is accessible through supported integrated development environments and on Go's package website³.

Choosing Go as the implementation language offers several advantages. Its cross-compilation process reduces platform dependencies, ensuring broad compatibility while generating high-performance executables. Moreover, Go's lightweight goroutines and channels simplify concurrent programming. The resulting system binaries are typically compact, around 10 MB, depending on application complexity.

Two important next steps in the development of this implementation are the integration of the Arrowhead Framework Ontology and the establishment of robust system authentication and authorization mechanisms. The ontology enables reasoning engines to infer new knowledge about the system-of-systems and to detect potential inconsistencies. Through queries, stakeholders can also interrogate the system-of-systems to obtain structured insights. From a security perspective, the current certificate authority indiscriminately issues certificates to any request; therefore, it is imperative that

systems are authenticated at runtime. Furthermore, attention must be directed toward the authorization system, where policies define which systems are permitted to consume specific services.

In summary, MBSE proves to be an effective approach in developing and deploying IoT frameworks while simplifying knowledge transfer and system maintenance. In the next section, we summarize our findings and discuss its broader implications for IoT development.

VII. CONCLUSION

Applying Model-Based Systems Engineering to the Arrowhead framework provides several benefits. First, models enhance knowledge transfer by visually representing system architecture and behavior. Second, the separation of concerns between systems and their unit assets improves configuration flexibility, removing the need for recompilation when making adjustments. Lastly, combining the Arrowhead framework's service-oriented architecture with the loosely coupled use cases in the mbaigo library supports scalable and resilient system design.

To gain practical insights into applying MBSE, readers are encouraged to explore the GitHub repositories linked to this work, which contain a functional implementation of the Arrowhead framework. The examples and opportunities to experiment with various systems provide a hands-on way for practitioners to explore real-world applications.

The implications of this work go beyond this specific implementation. MBSE can be applied to other IoT frameworks and architectures, enabling faster development, improved knowledge transfer, and more maintainable systems across industrial and commercial contexts. While the Arrowhead framework and IoT systems can be complex, this work demonstrates that such complexity does not inherently lead to complicated implementations.

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³<https://pkg.go.dev/github.com/sdoque/mbaigo>

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